

Barrier coating and plasmonic effect by using diamond-like carbon and silver nanoparticles on quantum dots sensitize solar cells

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Abstract

Effects of diamond-like carbon (DLC) and Ag nanoparticles (Ag NPs) on photoanode of quantum dot sensitized solar cell (QDSSCs) have studied for the first time. Photoanodes include thin films of the TiO₂ deposited on the FTO substrate, subsequently, graphene and CdS quantum dots (QDs) added on. Some photoanodes decorate by Ag nanoparticles and DLC thin film. Current density-voltage (J-V) characterization showed that the short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) and power conversion efficiency (PCE) of QDSSCs with localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) of Ag NPs and anti-corrosion, photon and electron barrier properties of DLC thin film increase photon harvesting and improve solar cells performance. J_{sc} of this configuration increased from about 8.87 to 14.6 mA cm², nearly doubled. The Ag NPs scatter photon and increase the photon harvesting in QDs. Results were showing that the presence of a thin film of DLC on TiO₂/CdS/G photoanodes increased the efficiency by 97%, short circuit current by 64%, and open circuit voltage by 16%. Also, the efficiency change from 0.8 to 1.58 in the presence of both DLC and Ag NPs in cells in compare with cells without Ag NPs and DLC.

Keywords: QDSSC, Photoanode, TiO₂, DLC thin film, Ag NPs; Electron Barrier, LSPR.